

Eclipse Soundscapes: Data Collector Submission

Introduction

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Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Submission

Thank you for participating in the Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Project as a Data Collector!

If you would like to increase the text size of this questionnaire please click "Low Vision Mode" in the top right corner.

Participating as an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector will support research on the effects of solar eclipses on the environment! Your submission is very important and research at this scale could not be done without your input! All recorded and submitted audio data and submitted audio data recording location information will be freely and publicly available with an attribution thanking volunteers for their contribution.

In addition to collecting data using the AudioMoth recording device and a MicroSD card, please use this form to enter information about the AudioMoth data recording location.

You will receive a certificate of completion after you submit your audio data by mailing the MicroSD card back to the Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) team. You can find mailing instructions on the [Data Collector page](#) on the ES website.

DIRECTIONS: Complete this form after you have collected AudioData for 5 days with your AudioMoth device. To complete this form you will need:

1. Your AudioMoth's ES ID #
2. Latitude and longitude of the AudioMoth's recording location [FORMAT: Decimal degrees (DD): 41.40338, 2.17403]
3. Audio data collection start time & end time

Eclipse Soundscapes Identification number (ES ID #) Info: If you received the AudioMoth from the ES team, the number is located on the outside of the AudioMoth box in braille and print. It is also located in print on the AudioMoth device itself in print in the bottom right corner of the device. If you did not receive your AudioMoth from the ES team you must [register your AudioMoth](#) on the ES website to receive a unique 3 digit ES ID #.

After submitting your data location information, you will be invited to participate in a survey about your experience. Your participation is entirely voluntary. Your responses to the survey will be separated from your data collection location submission to maintain confidentiality. Results from the survey will be reported in aggregate to evaluate the program's impact and support research efforts in determining how projects like this affect people's science identity.

Open Data Policy: Please see the "[Open Data Policy](#)" page on the EclipseSoundscapes.org website for more information about this policy and where ES data will be stored.

The entire process is expected to take 10-15 minutes. If you have any questions, feel free to contact David Bauer (dbauer@themarkusa.com) or Adrienne Celaya (acelaya@themarkusa.com).

VALIDATION %s format expected Using custom RegEx pattern Max character count = 5

DATA Shortname / Alias: **zip_code**

ID 232

1. What is your 5-digit zip code?

This might be different from the zip code where you completed the data collection. This information is shared with NASA Science Activation so that they can better understand where people are getting involved with the projects that they support.

If you do not know your zip code, or if you live outside of the United States, please enter 99999. *

Location

VALIDATION %s format expected Using custom RegEx pattern

DATA Shortname / Alias: **location**

ID 233

2. What is the location of your data collection? Please enter your location using your device's location or type in latitude and longitude in decimal degrees. (Example: 41.40338, 2.17403) *

Latitude

Longitude

DATA Shortname / Alias: **neighborhood**

ID 234

3. Please select the option that describes your outside observation location: *

- Urban / City
- Suburban
- Rural / Countryside

DATA Shortname / Alias: region

ID 235

4. Please select additional descriptions that describe your outside data collection location: Choose all that apply. *

- Park
- Forest
- Field or pasture
- Desert
- Beach
- Riverfront
- Lakefront
- Mountain area
- Hiking or Biking trail
- Zoo
- Farm

National Park, please specify:

National or State Forest, please specify:

Other, please specify:

DATA Shortname / Alias: **location_OE**

ID 236

5. Do you have additional information to share about your location? (For example, near a major road? Near a power generator or power supply station? Near particular animals/insects nesting/habitat? etc) Details and info always help!

DATA Shortname / Alias: **time_start**

ID 349

6. Data Collection Start Time:

What time did you begin your data collection? Please include the hour and minute separated by a colon (HH:MM format), using a 24-hour clock. Valid examples include 08:32 and 20:09. *

Please select your time zone: *

Eastern Time Zone
Central Time Zone
Mountain Time Zone
Pacific Time Zone
Alaska Time Zone
Hawaii-Aleutian Time Zone

DATA Shortname / Alias: **time_end**

ID 355

7. Data Collection Stop Time:

What time did you stop your data collection? Please include the hour and minute separated by a colon (HH:MM format), using a 24-hour clock. Valid examples include 08:32 and 20:09. *

Please select your time zone: *

Eastern Time Zone	▲
Central Time Zone	
Mountain Time Zone	
Pacific Time Zone	
Alaska Time Zone	
Hawaii-Aleutian Time Zone	▼

DATA Shortname / Alias: **audiomoth_ID**

ID 348

8. What is your AudioMoth's 3 digit ES ID#? *

Annular Eclipse Data Collector Submission

Page description:

Directions: Please follow the instructions below to submit your audio data.

ID 239

Audio Data Submission Instructions: In a padded envelope, please mail your MicroSD card to:

ES Team c/o ARISA Lab
47 High Street Ste 501
Medford, MA 02155

Please include a piece of paper with the following information:

- ES ID#
- Latitude/longitude of data recording location

The Eclipse Soundscapes Team is NOT able to return MicroSD cards to volunteers.

VALIDATION %s format expected

LOGIC Show/hide trigger exists.

DATA Shortname / Alias: **mail_SD**

ID 241

9. When will you mail your MicroSD Card?

Use this format - MM/DD/YYYY *

VALIDATION %s format expected

DATA Shortname / Alias: **email**

ID 363

10. Please provide your email address so we can check in with you on the MicroSD mailing and then email you a Data Collector Certificate. *

LOGIC Show/hide trigger exists.

DATA Shortname / Alias: **sci_starter_email**

ID 360

11. Would you like your SciStarter account to be credited for your participation?

- Yes
- No

VALIDATION %s format expected

LOGIC Hidden unless: #11 Question "Would you like your SciStarter account to be credited for your participation?" is one of the following answers ("Yes")

DATA Shortname / Alias: **sci_starter_email_OE**

ID 362

12. Please enter your SciStarter email address.

(untitled)

LOGIC Hidden unless: #9 Question "**When will you mail your MicroSD Card?**

Use this format - MM/DD/YYYY"

ID 331

Thank you, we will check in with you via email each week to confirm you have mailed your data. Once you've mailed your MicroSD to the ES team, you will receive a Data Collector Certificate via email.

Any questions, please contact info@EclipseSoundscapes.org.

Action: Webhook

New Webhook

Experience

DATA Shortname / Alias: **senses_pre**

ID 305

14. **BEFORE** being an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector, which of the following senses did you think you should use to make scientific observations? Choose all that apply. *

- Eyes / Sight
- Ears / Sound
- Touch/Feel
- Nose/Smell
- Tongue/Taste

DATA Shortname / Alias: **senses_post**

ID 306

15. Now, **AFTER** being an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector, which of the following senses do you think you should use to make scientific observations? Choose all that apply. *

- Eyes / Sight
- Ears / Sound
- Touch / Feel
- Nose / Smell
- Tongue / Taste

Experience Feedback

DATA Shortname / Alias: **interesting_OE**

ID 115

16. What was the most interesting thing that you learned during the last training or activity that you completed?

DATA Shortname / Alias: **esp_comments_OE**

ID 116

17. Do you have any comments about the last training or activity, or about the Eclipse Soundscapes Project in general, that you'd like to share?

DATA Shortname / Alias: **continue**

ID 94

18. Do you plan to continue participating in the ES Project?*

- Yes
- Maybe
- No, please explain:

LOGIC Show/hide trigger exists.

DATA Shortname / Alias: **interview**

ID 137

19. The evaluation team would like to interview some ES Project participants to learn more about their experiences. Do we have your permission to contact you in the future to request an interview? *

- Yes
- No, thank you

VALIDATION %s format expected

LOGIC Hidden unless: #19 Question "The evaluation team would like to interview some ES Project participants to learn more about their experiences. Do we have your permission to contact you in the future to request an interview?" is one of the following answers ("Yes")

DATA Shortname / Alias: **interview_email**

ID 358

20. Thank you for your willingness to participate in an interview. If you are selected for this opportunity, the evaluators will contact you via email to schedule the interview. Please provide your email address.

Demographics

DATA Shortname / Alias: **complete_method**

ID 225

21. How did you complete this Eclipse Soundscapes training or activity? *

- Self-paced online lessons
- In-person learning event (please specify location):
- Webinar learning event (please specify when / by whom):

DATA Shortname / Alias: **age**

ID 196

22. What is your age? *

- 13-17
- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65 and over
- Prefer not to say

DATA Shortname / Alias: **ethnicity**

ID 118

23. Please specify your ethnicity. Select all that apply. *

- African-American or Black
- Asian or Asian American
- Caucasian or White (non-Hispanic)
- Latinx or Hispanic
- Native American or Alaska Native
- Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
- Prefer to self-identify:
- Prefer not to say

DATA Shortname / Alias: **gender**

ID 119

24. How would you describe your gender? *

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary/non-conforming
- Prefer to self-describe:

- Prefer not to answer

DATA Shortname / Alias: **disability**

ID 168

25. The concept of disability used to imply an impairment of a person. In 2011, the World Health Organization redefined disability as a mismatch between the person and the environment they are in. Indeed, the social model of disability, which many members of the disability community identify with, states that it is not the person who is disabled, but the environment that disables them.

Do you have any long-term or chronic conditions that may impact your ability to move easily, see, hear, or speak, or to learn, remember, or concentrate or require ongoing accommodation? Please select all that apply. *

- No.
- Yes, Mobility: Difficulty walking, or walking for extended periods of time.
- Yes, Visual: Blindness, low vision, forms of color-blindness.
- Yes, Hearing: Deafness, hearing loss, severe tinnitus.
- Yes, Motor: Limited fine or gross motor control, e.g., tremors due to Parkinson's disease.
- Yes, Mental health conditions: Including depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, etc.
- Yes, Chronic illness: Various diagnoses; may involve chronic pain, fatigue, or other symptoms.
- Yes, Self Identify:
- Prefer not to answer

Thank You!

Thank you for your participation in the Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Project!

Your participation in the project was valuable and we appreciate it immensely.

We hope that you will continue to be involved in the project as an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Analyst!

If you have any questions, please contact David Bauer (Senior Evaluator at The Mark USA, Inc. | dbauer@themarkusa.com) or MaryKay Severino (Education Director at ARISA Labs, LLC | ESCSP_pi@arisalab.org).

Sincerely,

The Eclipse Soundscapes Project Team

[Click here to return to the Eclipse Soundscapes website.](#)